

ATTITUDE OF HEALTH WORKERS AND ITS EFFECT TOWARD THE CARE AND MANAGEMENT OF PEOPLE LIVING WITH HIV/AIDS IN JAMA'A LGA, KAFANCHAN, KADUNA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS) is a global health challenge today, but the attitude of health workers towards HIV patients has become a greater challenge in our health care system today. This has continued overtime and has become a major concern today as it has become a major threat to our public health system. This study has thus investigated the attitude of health workers and its effects on the care and management of people living with HIV/AIDS in Jam'a Local Government Area (LGA) of Kaduna state. The study was a cross-sectioned survey using One Hundred and Eleven (111) Respondents through a simple random technique. Data were collated using a semi-structured questionnaire consisting of 12-point attitude scale rated <7,7-12 as negative and positive attitude respectively for measuring attitude of health workers towards the care and management of HIV/AIDS patients. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and chi-square test at $p < 0.05$. The age of respondents was 31.3 ± 8.2 years while 70.30% of the respondents were females. 23.0% of the respondents showed negative attitude with a mean attitude score of 7.9 ± 2.9 . Some of the questions that the respondents affirmed include; refusing admission to HIV/AIDS patients (8.1%), people with HIV/AIDS should be admitted into a separate ward (26.7%), different behavior to HIV/AIDS patients compared with other patients (21.6%). Most of the respondents (53.2%) reported that they have seen health workers verbally maltreating HIV/AIDS patients. These reported attitudes of health workers on HIV/AIDS patients has resulted in some great consequences among people living with HIV/AIDS which include; refusal to seek further medical attention (88.3%), violent actions (91.0%), suicidal tendencies (90.1%), reluctance to provide further medical history that could enhance recovery/wanting to spread the infection (85.6%). This study revealed that the attitude of health workers revealed towards has significantly affected their recovery and management. Therefore continuous education/counselling of health workers on HIV/AIDS, provision of policies against discriminatory/stigmatizing attitude of HIV/AIDS patients should be put in place in all health care facilities.

INTRODUCTION

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infection and AIDS remain a major public health crises in Nigeria. As at the end of 2012, UNAIDS reported that there are about 3.4 million people living with AIDS in Nigeria out of the 22.5 million in sub-saharan Africa. This figure places Nigeria second to south Africa with the highest number of people living with HIV/AIDS globally (UNAIDS, 2012).

In 2011, Nigeria was reported to have the highest number of new HIV infections (WHO/UNAIDS, 2011). while in 2010, the country was estimated to have 360,000 children living with HIV, most of who became infected from their mothers (UNAIDS, 2010).

The emergence of HIV/AIDS has created a lot of tension among health care providers as there is this palpable

any mistake in the workplace while attending to HIV/AIDS patients could lead to contracting the infection. The consequences of this perception has resulted in a negative attitude in the management of people living with HIV/AIDS that require treatment and support (Kermode, 2005). Effective and efficient care for these patients can only be possible when positive attitudes are maintained by health care providers in the treatment and management of HIV/AIDS patients (walvsimbi).

Therefore, this study investigated the attitude of health care workers and the resultant effect in the care and management of people living with HIV/AIDS in Jama'a Local Government Area of Kaduna state.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted among health workers in some selected health facilities in Jama'a Local Government Area (LGA) of Kafanchan in Kaduna state.

Jama'a Local Government is the southern part of Kaduna state with headquarters in Kafanchan about 150 kilometers away from Kaduna city metropolis. It is surrounded by neighbouring states like Nassarawa state, Plateau state and the Federal Capital Territory Abuja. It has an area of about 1.661km² and a population of 278,735 according to the 2006 census. This local government area has about 220 registered health care workers.

The research design was a descriptive cross-sectional survey method which

investigated the attitude of health workers towards the management and treatment of people living with HIV/AIDS in selected health facilities/centres in the Local Government Area.

The sample size for this study was calculated using EPI INFO statistical package and the following parameters were entered into STATCAL: population size of 220, expected requery of 18% and worst acceptable size obtainable value for 5% as indicated by Muzuwalo (2011). Simple random sampling technique was used to select health workers in all units and wards in selected health facilities until the sample size was met. This was to enable elements of the choosing population have equal and independent chance of being included in the sample. After imputation of these parameters, the sample size obtained was 112 at 95% confidence level.

A well designed structured questionnaire was used in data collection after informed consent of the Hospital Management Board and Study Participant were obtained. The questionnaire consisted of five sections. The first section was designed to obtain personal data /information of the respondents while the other sections contained items on the research question on the attitude and effects of health workers towards the care and management of PLWHA.

The research instrument was pretested among 10% of a population with characteristics consistent with the study population to check for consistency. This gave a co-efficient of 0.75 indicating a positive reliability of the instrument.

The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents with the help of some personnel in the selected health facilities. The respondents were given reasonable time within which to respond to the issues raised in the questionnaire was collected by the researcher for data analysis.

The quality of data obtained was examined thoroughly to review pattern of response of each participant as recorded in the questionnaire and necessary adjustments were made afterwards. Serial numbers were assigned to the questionnaire for easy identification and recall of any instrument with issues. A 12-point attitude of health workers was included in the questionnaire; positive answers were allocated 0. The 12-points attitude of health workers was included in the questionnaire; positive answers were allocated 1, while negative answers were allocated 0. The 12-points attitude of health workers scale was rated >7 and <7 for negative and positive attitude respectively.

Data were analysed using descriptive statistics i.e., mean, frequency, percentage and standard deviation and inferential statistics which included chi-

square test for the hypothesis at $P < 0.05$ significant level and presented in tables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-demographics of respondents show that their mean age was 31.3 ± 8.2 and most within the 20-29 years age range. 70.3% of them were females while 65.8% were single. Most respondents were nurses and, 95.5% of them are Christians and 40% of them had worked for about 4 years (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents.

The socio-demographics of respondents indicates that a large percentage of young, single female nurses with working experience ranging from 1-4 years. The response obtained also shows that majority of these workers have been exposed to HIV/AIDS Training in the past 2-3 years. (Table 2).

Table 2: Exposure to workshop on HIV/AIDS.

EXPOSURE TO TRAINING ON HIV/AIDS

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Previous Exposure to HIV/AIDS		
Training		
Yes	85	76.6
No	26	23.4
Total	111	100
Training attended in the past:		
0-1 years	27	31.8
2-3 years	43	50.6
4-5 years	8	9.4
Above 5 years	7	8.2
Total	85	100

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Age in years		
20-29	60	54.1
30-39	32	28.8
40 and Above	19	17.1
Total	111	100
Gender		
Male	33	29.7
Female	78	70.3
Total	111	100
Marital status		
Single	73	65.8
Married	35	31.5
Divorced	0	0.00
Widow	3	2.7
Total	111	100
Professional status		
Physician	7	6.3
Nurses	81	73.0
Laboratory scientist	8	7.2
CHO/CHEW	15	13.5
Total	111	100
Religion		
Christianity	106	95.5
Islam	5	4.5
Pagan	0	0.0
Total	111	100

ITEMS	AGREED N (%)	DISAGREE N(%)	TOTAL N(%)
Professionals should be educated against discriminatory practice and its effects on PLWHA	107(96.4)	4(3.6)	111(100.0)
Policy should be implemented to kick against discrimination of HIV/AIDS patients	90(81.1)	21(18.9)	111(100.0)
Discriminating attitude of staff against PLWHA should be penalized	95(85.6)	16(14.4)	111(100.0)
Availability of equipments and facilities for care motives staff towards PLWHA	101(91.0)	16(9.0)	111(100.0)
The proper adoption of universal precautions assist health workers to provide care to HIV/AIDS patients	106(95.4)	6(4.6)	111(100.0)

Based on the table above, it is expected that most of the health workers (85%) who have been exposed to HIV/AIDS training should bring such training to bear in their attitude towards HIV/AIDS patients.

In line with this study, a study in federal medical centre owo, ondo state in the attitude and practice of health care workers towards HIV positive patients reported similar mean age, Religious background and specialization with nurses representing the highest percentage (Ebenezer, 2014).

Respondents (73.0%) attitude towards HIV/AIDS patients was positive with a mean age of 7.9 ± 31.3 . However, some respondents have negative attitude toward HIV/AIDS patients and they agreed to refusing admission to HIV/AIDS patients (8.1%) and even revealed that they suggested that people with HIV/AIDS should be admitted into a separate ward (26.7%). Some even believe that treating an HIV/AIDS patient is a waste of time and resources (1.8%). Some even

alluded to the fact that they don't mind insulting HIV/AIDS patients knowingly or unknowingly (6.3%). These indicates a serious negative

attitude towards HIV/AIDS patients (22.6%) as more than half of these respondents admitted that they have seen other healthcare workers obviously maltreating HIV/AIDS patients as early observed by Muziwalo et al; (2011).

These negative attitudes are generally based on the beliefs of healthcare professionals that HIV/AIDS patients are responsible for their situation because of their immoral and deviant behavior. Compromising and discriminatory attitudes towards patients with HIV/AIDS have also been reported by Aisien and Shobowale, 2005; Delobelle et'al, 2009; Ehlers, 2006; Lehmann and Zulu, 2005; amongst others.

Older respondents showed less negative attitude towards HIV/AIDS patients than younger professionals (Table 3).

Table 3: Association between age or respondents and their previous exposure to training on HIV/AIDS (H₀1).

Table 4: Solutions to the negative attitude of health workers towards patients living with HIV/AIDS.

It is therefore imperative that HIV/AIDS related stigmatization should be adequately tackled to avoid negative interference with the universal uptake of ARVs and improve care and management of HIV/AIDS.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adebando, S.B., Bamgbala, A.O, Oyediran, M.A, (2003) Attitude of health care providers for person living with HIV/AIDS in Lagos State, Nigeria. *African Reprove Health*; 7: 103-112
- 2) Adetoyede. Y.O., Bashir, O.O., Ibrahim, S.BB (2007). physicians and HIV and knowledge influence their attitude & comfort in rendering care *Afr J. Health Science* (14:37-43)
- 3) Adeyi (2006). The epidemiology of HIV/AIDS in Nigeria. *Havard centre for population and development studies*.
- 4) Aisien, A.O, Shobowale, M.O., (2005). Health care workers knowledge on HIV/AIDS : universal precautions and attitude towards PLWHA in Benin-City, Nigeria. *Niger J. Clin. Pract.* 8(2): 74-82
- 5) Alubo, O., Zwandor, A., Jolayemi, T., Omudo, E., (2002). Acceptance and stigmatization of PLWHA in Nigeria. *AIDS Care* 14:117-126
- 6) Delobelle, P., Rawlinson, J.I., Ntuli, s., Malatsi, I., Decock, R., (2009). HIV/AIDS knowledge, attitudes, practices and perceptions of rural nurses in South Africa. *Journal Adv Nurs*; 65(5): 1061-1073
- 7) Ebenezer, O.D., (2014). Attitude and practices of health care workers towards HIV positive patients at the Federal Medical Centre Owo, Ondo State Nigeria. *South American Journal of Public health*; 2(4): 1-44
- 8) Ehlers, V.J., (2006). Challenges nurses face in coping with the HIV/AIDS pandemic in Africa. *Int J Nurs Stud*; 43 (6): 657-662
- 9) Kardas- Nelson M. (2012). How to tackle HIV Stigma among health care workers. www.aidsmap.com page 245-4641/ website published (02 August, 2012)
- 10) Lehmann, U., Zulu, J., (2005). How nurses in Cape town clinics experience the HIV epidemic. *AIDS Bulletin*; 14(1): 7
- 11) Marchal, B., Brouwere, V.D., Kegels, G., (2005). Viewpoint: HIV/AIDS and the health workforce crisis : what are the nextsteps? *Trop Med Int Health*; 10(4): 300-304
- 12) Muhammad, B.H and Kippax, S., (2005). HIV related discriminatory attitudes of health care workers in Bangedesh. *J. Health Popul Nutr.* 28(2)

- 13) Muziwalo, V.M., Supa, P., and Karl, P., (2011). Nurse knowledge, attitude and coping related to HIV and AIDS in a rural Hospital in South Africa. *Ethno Med*, 5(1): 25-320
- 14) Ntuli, A.K, Julieth, S.E.M., (2011). Perceived barriers and attitudes of health care providers towards provider-Initiated HIV Testing and Counselling in Mbeya region, southern highland zone of Tanzania. *Pan African Medical Journal*: 8(17)
- 15) Omo, O.E., Elegbede, O.F., Agboola, S.T., Isinkaye, A.O., Omopariola, O.A (2013). Effects of Stigmatization/Discrimination among HIV/AIDS infected patients in rural tertiary Meducav centre in Nigeria. *J. Int Assoc provide AIDS care* (00:1-4)
- 16) Reis, C., Heisle, M., Amowitz, L.L., Moreland, R.S., Mafeni, J.O., (2005). Discriminatory attitudes and practices by health workers toward patients with HIV/AIDS in Nigeria. *PLoS Med*; 2(8): 246
- 17) -Sadob, W.E., Oladimeji, A.O., Sotiloye, O.S., (2006). Attitude of health-care workers to HIV/AIDS *Afr. J. Reprod Health* 1:39-46
- 18) Sadob, W.E., Oladimeji, A.O., Sotiloye, O.S., (2006). Attitude of Health care workers to HIV/AIDS *Afr. J. Reprod Health* (10)1:39-46
- 19) UNAIDS & UNICEF (2008). Toward Universal access scaling up priority HIV/AIDS intervention in the health sector
- 20) UNAIDS (2008). Report on the Global AIDS epidemic
- 21) UNAIDS, (2000). BEST Practice Collection Protocol for the identification of discrimination against people living with HIV. UNAIDS, GENEVA
- 22) UNICEF, (2012). STATE OF THE WORLD'S children 2012. Unicef, New York, USA
- 23) UNDP (2007/2008) Human Development reports.
- 24) UNAIDS (2008). Epidemiological fact sheet on HIV and AIDS.
- 25) Walu Simbi M; Okonsky J.G; (2004). Knowledge and attitude of nurses caring for patients with HIV/AIDS in Uganda, 2004; 17;92-99
- 26) WHO (2008) Report on the Global AIDS Epidemic.
- 27) Zelnick, J., O'Donnell, M., (2005). THE IMPACT OF THE hiv/aids epidemic on hospital nurses in KwaZulu Natal, South Africa: nurses' perspectives and implications for health policy. *J Public Health Policy*; 26(2): 163-185.